

Development and Characterization of Thermoresponsive Double-Network Nanocomposite Hydrogel for Bone Tissue Engineering

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In this study, a thermoresponsive double-network (DN) nanocomposite hydrogel is developed. The primary hydrogel network comprises Pluronic P123, while the secondary network comprises gelatinmethacrylate (GELMA) and polyacrylamide (PAM). A systematic approach is adopted to develop DN hydrogels. Initially, the impact of Pluronic P123 concentration on the mechanical properties of PAM-GELMA hydrogel is investigated. Results from the tensile strength and the oscillatory shear tests reveal that an increasing P123 concentration has a marginal effect on the storage modulus while significantly reducing the loss modulus of the PAM-GELMA hydrogel, thereby improving mechanical properties. Notably, DN3 hydrogel containing 7.5 w/v% P123 in PAM-GELMA exhibits osteoid matrix-like mechanical properties. To further enhance the mechanical properties, citrate-containing amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP_CIT) is incorporated in DN3 hydrogel at varying concentrations. At a lower concentration of ACP_CIT (0.75 w/v%), the mechanical properties of DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogel are notably enhanced. Incorporating ACP_CIT in DN3 hydrogel (DN3-ACP0.75) decreases creep strain, rapid stress relaxation, and reduced water uptake capacity while maintaining the thermoresponsive behavior. Finally, an *in vitro* analysis confirms the cytocompatibility of the hydrogels with MC3T3-E1 cells, indicating the potential use in bone tissue engineering.

1. Introduction

Bone tissue engineering (BTE) has been significantly advancing, driven by the need for effective solutions to bone defects and injuries. Conventional autologous bone grafting method has limitations such as donor site morbidity, increased blood loss, and limited availability.^[1] As a result, there is growing interest in developing synthetic alternatives that can mimic the natural bone environment and promote tissue regeneration.^[2–5] In subsequent years, materials such as ceramics, metal nanoparticles, bioglass, polymers, and proteins alone or in combination were utilized.^[6,7,16,8–15] Hydrogels have emerged as a potential candidate due to their high water content, tunable mechanical and chemical properties, low immunogenicity, nutrient permeability, porosity, and biocompatibility.^[17,18]

Hydrogels are a 3D network of crosslinked hydrophilic polymers formed through covalent bonds or physical intra- or intermolecular interactions, which provide 3D confinement to cells, which can

potentially recapitulate the extracellular matrix (ECM).^[19] Hydrogels serve as scaffolds playing critical roles in 1) delivering seeded cells to target sites, 2) facilitating cell-biomaterial interactions, 3) promoting cell adhesion, 4) providing nutrients, growth factors, 5) supporting cell survival, differentiation, proliferation, and differentiation, and 6) controlling structure and function of the engineered tissue.^[20–24]

Despite several advantages, conventional single-network hydrogels in BTE possess poor mechanical properties compared to the living ECM, and their application under load or tension is not realistic.^[25] In the fabrication of synthetic hydrogel, a heterogeneous network is formed by crosslinking that tends to deform when stress is concentrated on a short chain with low molecular weight, resulting in crack formation and disrupting the 3D network.^[26] Various attempts were utilized to toughen the hydrogel, such as sliding-ring hydrogel, nanocomposite hydrogel, double network hydrogel, and macromolecular microsphere composite hydrogel.^[27–30] Amongst these, double network (DN) hydrogels have demonstrated tunable mechanical strength, high toughness, and unique network topologies, attracting intense research interest to develop novel hydrogel systems.^[31,32]

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Figure 1. The DN hydrogel was developed through a physical-chemical network, in which the primary network was formed by Pluronic P123 self-assembly, while the secondary network consisted of PAM-GELMA crosslinked using APS and TEMED. Additionally, ACP_CIT was incorporated as the inorganic component to create nanocomposite hydrogels.

DN hydrogel consists of two interpenetrating polymer networks with contrasting mechanical properties.^[33,34] One of the polymer networks consists of hard and brittle sacrificial bonds, while the other provides soft and flexible networks.^[35] This unique combination of properties makes DN hydrogel suitable for flexible and durable applications. The DN hydrogels can be fabricated using various techniques such as chemically-chemically crosslinked, physically-chemically crosslinked, lamellar bilayer network, or micro/nanocomposite network. The first network is constructed by physically crosslinked gel in the physically-chemically hybrid networks, while the second network is fabricated by chemically crosslinked gel.^[36] The association of the two networks is due to hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, or van der Waals interaction, depending on the polymer properties.^[37] A brief overview of the biomaterials used to synthesize DN hydrogels over the past decade is presented in Table S1 (Supporting Information).

Incorporating thermoresponsive behavior into DN hydrogels adds another layer of functionality. The thermoresponsive hydrogel undergoes shape transition. The reversible transition between shapes leads to the shape memory effect (SME), originating from a DN hydrogel.^[38,39] One of the polymer networks in thermoresponsive consists of hard and brittle sacrificial bonds, a phase that maintains the original shape and prevents flow deformation of the DN hydrogel. The second polymer provides a soft, flexible network that acts as a reversible phase to fix the temporary shape.^[35] Such materials have been gaining attention due to their shape tuneability, which holds promise for treating irregular bone defects and targeted drug release.^[40]

Incorporating nanomaterials is explored to enhance the properties of the DN hydrogels further. The micro/nanocomposite hydrogel provides a sacrificial bond that effectively yields and decapitates energy on deformation.^[31] Moreover, nanocomposite hydrogels are preferred in BTE applications as they can potentially recapitulate the extracellular matrix (ECM). Various materials, including hydroxyapatite,^[41–43] calcium polyphosphate,^[44] octacalcium phosphate,^[45] calcium silicate,^[46] bioglass,^[47] and graphene oxide,^[48] have been used to reinforce hydrogel for BTE applications.

In this study, we have utilized Pluronic P123 to form the first polymer network, as it self-associates in an aqueous solution to create a micellar structure within a diameter of 100 nm.^[49] The second polymeric network was formed using co-polymerizing polyacrylamide (PAM) and gelatin methacrylate (GELMA). Citrate-containing amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP_CIT) was incorporated in P123-PAM-GELMA hydrogels for developing nanocomposite hydrogels, as shown in **Figure 1**.

Pluronic P123 is a polymer consisting of hydrophilic polyethylene oxide (PEO) and hydrophobic polypropylene oxide (PPO) arranged in tri-block PEO-PPO-PEO, widely used in drug delivery and tissue engineering applications due to its excellent biocompatibility and thermo-sensitivity.^[50] It possesses thermoreversible behavior below critical gelation temperature (20–30 °C).^[49] This behavior of Pluronic P123 is reversible, meaning that the solution undergoes gel formation on cooling. However, Pluronic P123 has poor mechanical properties, so PAM and GELMA were utilized to enhance mechanical strength.

PAM is widely used due to its easy polymerization and stable crosslinking network. In the 1980s, PAM hydrogels were

first used in aesthetic surgery. Since then, this material has been widely used in ophthalmic operations, wound dressing, water treatment, food packaging products, and cell-based applications.^[51] Recently, a commercial viscosupplement (Con-tura's Astrosemid) was introduced, comprising PAM. A 52-week human study demonstrated the efficiency of Astrosemid in treating knee osteoarthritis.^[52] PAM hydrogels possess nearly perfect elasticity but lack cell attachment sites and thermo-sensitivity.^[53] One possibility is to deploy gelatin methacrylate (GELMA) to overcome this problem. Gelatin contains the RGD (arginine-glycine-aspartic acid) peptide sequence essential for cell adhesion.^[54] Moreover, the methacrylate groups of GELMA can be crosslinked using ammonium persulfate (APS) and tetramethyl-ethylenediamine (TEMED), which also crosslinks PAM.^[55,56] Therefore, the second hydrogel network is formed by a copolymer of GELMA-PAM.

ACP is a central precursor in biomineralization.^[57] It is a bio-compatible and bioresorbable calcium phosphate widely used in biomedical applications, including bone regeneration and drug delivery. One major drawback of ACP is its metastable nature, leading to rapid apatite transformation.^[58] The transformation of ACP to apatite can be delayed by two mechanisms: surface absorption of organic molecules (adenosine triphosphate (ATP), polyelectrolyte, citrate, and polyethylene glycol) or ionic substitution (magnesium, zinc, iron, carbonates, pyrophosphates, and fluorine).^[59-63] We have used citrate-containing amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP_CIT) to develop nanocomposite P123-PAM-GELMA hydrogels.

The study aims to develop and characterize a novel thermore-sponsive nanocomposite DN hydrogel for BTE applications. For this, we have followed a systematic approach; initially, the impact of varying w/v concentrations of P123 (2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10%) on mechanical and rheological properties (Young's modulus, tensile strength, elongation at break) of PAM-GELMA was evaluated. Amongst these, the DN hydrogel with 7.5 w/v% P123 in PAM-GELMA (DN3) exhibited the mechanical properties close to native osteoid matrix (Young's modulus \approx 60 kPa). Therefore, it was further utilized to develop nanocomposite DN hydrogels by incorporating different w/v concentrations of ACP_CIT (0.75%, 1.5%, and 3%). The nanocomposite DN hydrogels with 0.75 w/v% ACP_CIT (DN3-ACP0.75) exhibited the osteoid matrix-like mechanical properties. Overall, the study focuses on synthesis, mechanical characterization, and cytocompatibility assessment of the developed DN hydrogels, providing insights into their potential application in BTE.

2. Experimental Section

Calcium citrate tetrahydrate (CAS 5785-44-4), trisodium phosphate (CAS 7601-54-9), sodium hydroxide (CAS 1301-73-2), ammonium persulfate (CAS 7727-54-0), and *N, N, N', N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine (CAS 110-18-9) were procured from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. 30% acrylamide/*N, N'*-methylenebisacrylamide solution (37.5:1) (PAM premix) was received from Bio-Rad, USA, and \approx 50% methacrylate gelatin (GELMA) was obtained from Cellink, Sweden. Hanks balanced salt solution (HBSS) was acquired from Gibco Life Technologies, Germany.

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of Citrate Stabilized Amorphous Calcium Phosphate

Synthesis of ACP_CIT was performed using the previously reported protocol.^[64] Briefly: The reaction was performed in a volume of 300 mL. Initially, 150 mL of 50×10^{-3} M of calcium citrate solution was prepared in Milli-Q water (Millipore, Bedford, USA), followed by pH adjustment to 11.5 using 2 M sodium hydroxide. Subsequently, 150 mL of 100×10^{-3} M trisodium phosphate solution was rapidly added into 150 mL of 50×10^{-3} M of calcium citrate solution. The precipitate was isolated by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 5 min and washed thrice with Milli-Q water. Centrifuge tubes containing the precipitates were immersed in liquid nitrogen for 15 min, followed by freeze-drying for 72 h. The obtained powder was preserved in airtight containers for further characterization.

The phase composition of synthesized ACP_CIT was determined using X-ray diffraction using a PANalytical AERIS diffractometer (PANalytical X'Pert PRO MPD, equipped with a Cu tube (Cu $K\alpha = 1.54$ Å) The Netherlands). The diffraction data were collected at 40 kV and 15 mA in a step mode with a step size of 0.04° , in the 2θ range from 10 to 70° .

The Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed using a Nicolet iS50 FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Experiments were performed in transmission mode from the wavenumber ranging from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} (64 scans).

The morphology and particle size of synthesized ACP_CIT were evaluated by FEG-TEM (Tecnai G2 F30, USA) operated at 300 kV. The sample preparation was as follows: a small amount of powder was dispersed in isopropyl alcohol and sonicated in an ultrasonic bath. Further, the samples were placed on a carbon-coated grid and dried before analysis.

2.2. Synthesis of DN Hydrogel

The primary solution was prepared by making Pluronic's P123 prepared in Milli-Q water at different w/v concentrations (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%). The secondary solution was prepared by incorporating 2 w/v% GELMA in PAM premix solution and mixed at 500 rpm for 30 min to get a homogenous solution. The DN hydrogels were prepared by mixing an equal amount of primary (3 mL) and secondary solutions (3 mL). Afterward, 100 μ L (10 w/v%) APS and 10 μ L TEMED were added for crosslinking. The solution was vortexed and immediately added into the rectangular molds, which were allowed to be set for 30 min at 37°C .

Nanocomposite DN hydrogels were prepared by adding different w/v concentrations of 1.5%, 3%, and 6% of ACP_CIT in 15 w/v% Pluronic's P123 solution. The secondary solution was prepared by mixing 2 w/v% GELMA in PAM premix solution and mixed for 30 min to get a homogenous solution. The nanocomposite DN hydrogels were prepared by mixing 3 mL of primary and 3 mL of secondary solution. Afterward, 100 μ L APS and 10 μ L TEMED were added for crosslinking. The solution was vortexed and immediately added into the rectangular molds, which were allowed to be set for 30 min at 37°C .

DN hydrogel was synthesized by mixing equal amounts of GELMA-PAM and Pluronic's P123 solution; therefore, the effec-

Table 1. Abbreviations and effective GELMA, PAM, P123, and ACP_CIT concentrations in the respective DN hydrogel.

Hydrogel	Effective concentration in hydrogel				Abbreviations
	GELMA w/v%	PAM w/v%	P123 w/v%	ACP_CIT w/v%	
PAM-GELMA	1	30	–	–	PAM-GELMA
GELMA-PAM-(5 w/v%) P123	1	15	2.5	–	DN1
GELMA-PAM-(10 w/v%) P123	1	15	5	–	DN2
GELMA-PAM-(15 w/v%) P123	1	15	7.5	–	DN3
GELMA-PAM-(20 w/v%) P123	1	15	10	–	DN4
DN3-(1.5 w/v%) ACP_CIT	1	15	7.5	0.75	DN3-ACP0.75
DN3-(3 w/v%) ACP_CIT	1	15	7.5	1.5	DN3-ACP1.5
DN3-(6 w/v%) ACP_CIT	1	15	7.5	3	DN3-ACP3

tive concentration of the respective compounds was reduced to half. The abbreviation of hydrogels and their effective concentrations are represented in Table 1. These abbreviations were used in all the following sections.

2.3. Tensile Properties

The uniaxial tensile test was performed on the fabricated hydrogels, and the mechanical properties were analyzed using the universal testing machine Instron 5967 (Instron GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany). The hydrogel was fabricated in a rectangular mold, having a 9 mm width and 20 mm length. The analysis was performed at a 5 mm min⁻¹ crosshead speed at 100 N load cell. Mechanical properties such as Young's modulus, tensile strength, and elongation at break were analyzed using a tensile stress-strain curve.

2.4. Oscillatory Shear Tests

Oscillatory shear tests (TA HR20 rheometer, New Castle, USA) used a 20 mm parallel cross-hatched Peltier plate, and the solvent trap was used. The linear viscoelastic region (LVE) was analyzed by amplitude sweep analysis performed under a constant frequency of 1 Hz and shear strain ranging from 1 to 100%. The loss moduli (G'') and storage moduli (G') were characterized by the frequency sweep analysis performed under 1% shear strain, and frequency ranged from 0.1 to 10 Hz. A constant static force of 10 N was applied for creep experiments, and the temperature was kept constant at 25 °C throughout the experiment for 180 s. The stress relaxation experiments were performed at a constant strain of 1%, and a shear stress of 1 kPa was applied to the hydrogel for 180 s. Further strain was removed, and the recovery phase was registered for 360 s.

2.5. Water Uptake Capacity

The water uptake capacity was tested using a gravimetric procedure. Initially, the weight of dry samples was recorded (W_0). Subsequently, the dry samples were immersed in 20 mL Milli-Q water. The sample was removed at different time points till 720 min.

The excess water from the sample was removed using moist filter paper, and the weight was recorded (W_1). The samples' water uptake capacity (W%) was calculated using Equation (1).

$$W\% = \left(\frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

2.6. Thermo-responsive Behavior

Samples were prepared in rectangular molds of length of 45 mm and width of 15 mm to analyze the hydrogel's shape memory behavior. The prepared samples were swelled in Milli-Q water for 24 h and further treated in 70 °C Milli-Q water for 2 min. Afterward, the samples were removed, and a temporary cylindrical shape was formed by wrapping the samples. The temporary shape was fixed by placing the samples in 4 °C Milli-Q water for 2 min. The shape recovery process from the transformed shape to the original shape was triggered by immersing samples in 70 °C Milli-Q water. Five cycles of temporary shape formation and its recovery to the original shape were performed.

2.7. In Vitro Analysis

2.7.1. Cell Culture Maintenance

An osteoblast precursor cell line derived from mouse (*Mus musculus*) calvaria (MC3T3-E1, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) was employed for cellular analysis after ten passages. MC3T3-E1 cells were maintained in an α -MEM medium containing 10 vol% fetal bovine serum (Gibco Life Science, USA) and 10 vol% penicillin–streptomycin (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂. The cultures of MC3T3-E1 cells were trypsinized by adding 3 mL of trypsin–EDTA solution. When the cells were detached, 9 mL of α -MEM medium was added to the T75 flask. The cells were counted, and 1 × 10⁵ cells mL⁻¹ were inoculated into fresh T75 flasks, followed by incubation at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂.

Figure 2. Characterization of ACP_CIT (A) X-ray diffraction patterns confirming the amorphous nature of ACP_CIT. (B) FTIR spectrum displaying functional groups present in the ACP_CIT. (C) FEG-TEM confirmed ≈ 40 nm particle size of ACP_CIT nanoparticles.

2.7.2. Cell Harvesting

Cell culture media was removed from the T75 flask, adding 5 mL of sterile Dulbecco's phosphate buffer saline (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) to dislodge attached cells and remove cell fractions. Then, the PBS was discarded, adding 3 mL of Trypsin-EDTA (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) solution for 3–5 min and incubating at 37 °C for 3–5 min. After detachment of cells, 9 mL of α -MEM was added and mixed well and then transferred to a centrifuge tube at 350 rpm for 2 min to acquire cell pellet, which was further redispersed in 3 mL of α -MEM medium and mixed well. 100 μ L of the cell suspension was transferred to 96-well plates, 100 μ L of trypan blue was added, and cells were further counted using a Neubauer chamber (Neubauer-improved, Paul Marienfeld GmbH and Co.KG, Germany). A solution containing 25 000 cells per mL was prepared and centrifuged at 500 rpm for 2 min to acquire a cell pellet.

2.7.3. Cell Encapsulation

All the solutions were sterilized by passing through 0.22 μ m filters. All operations were performed on a sterile bench. The DN and nanocomposite DN hydrogels were synthesized using the procedure illustrated in Section 2.2. After forming respective solutions, the cell pellet was mixed to form a cell suspension, followed by the addition of 100 μ L APS and 10 μ L TEMED. The solution was gently aspirated and immediately added into the 12-mm diameter and 2-mm height circular mold using a positive displacement pipette set for 30 min at 37 °C.

CellCrown inserts (ScaffdexOy, Tampere, Finland) were placed in a six-well plate. The circular mold was removed, and the hydrogels were transferred onto the CellCrown. 2 mL of α -MEM medium was added to each well and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 95% air and 5% CO₂. The α -MEM medium was changed every 2 d.

2.7.4. Rhodamine Phalloidin/ DAPI Stain

The hydrogels were washed with HBSS and treated with 4% paraformaldehyde in HBSS for 15 min, then washed thrice with

HBSS. Subsequently, a permeability buffer was introduced for 5 min, after which it was removed carefully. Further, a Phalloidin-master mix (8 μ L Phalloidin per mL of HBSS) was added following incubation for one hour in the dark. Afterward, the Phalloidin-master mix was removed, and constructs were washed with HBSS. Then, the constructs were stained with DAPI (1 μ L DAPI per mL of HBSS) for 15 min in the dark. The constructs were once again washed with HBSS and analyzed on an inverted epifluorescence microscope (Axio scope 1, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany). Three replicates were analyzed, and cell viability was determined.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterization

X-ray amorphous ACP_CIT is shown in **Figure 2A**. The amorphous nature of ACP_CIT was also analyzed using FTIR analysis. The phosphate groups of ACP_CIT show three vibration peaks of ν_1 , ν_3 , and ν_4 , which were observed at 950, 1020, and 560 cm⁻¹, respectively. The non-splitting peak observed at 560 cm⁻¹ confirmed the amorphous nature of ACP_CIT.^[57] The functional groups of citrate were analyzed using FTIR analysis, shown in **Figure 2B**. The band observed at 3250 cm⁻¹ corresponds to OH asymmetric and symmetric stretching, and the band at 1670 cm⁻¹ signifies the OH bending mode of water. Furthermore, the bands observed at 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1446 cm⁻¹ represent COO bending and COH stretching, respectively, of the carboxylic group in citrates.^[65] The spherical morphology of the ACP_CIT particle was confirmed by FEG-TEM, as shown in **Figure 2C**.

3.2. Synthesis of DN Hydrogel

All the synthesized hydrogels are shown in **Figure 3**. The PAM-GELMA forms transparent hydrogels. The transparency was retained by blending 2.5% P123 (w/v) in PAM-GELMA hydrogel and increasing concentration to 5% (w/v) P123, making translucent hydrogels PAM-GELMA, further increase in P123 concentration (7.5% and 10%) results in opaque hydrogels. Therefore,

Figure 3. Photograph of synthesized hydrogels. As the concentration of P123 increases in the PAM-GELMA hydrogel, the transparency is compromised.

at higher concentrations of Pluronic P123, the transparent nature of PAM-GELMA hydrogels was compromised. At higher concentrations of Pluronic P123, the intrinsic arrangement of micelles and entanglement of the polymer chain within the PAM-GELMA hydrogel contribute to the structural complexity of Pluronic P123, leading to light scattering and making gels opaque.^[66] Moreover, previous studies have shown that an increase in the Pluronic P123 results in bigger micelles size, which may also be responsible for the increase in the opacity of the hydrogel.^[49]

3.3. Mechanical Analysis

Uniaxial tensile strength analysis revealed the synthesized hydrogels' mechanical properties (see **Figure 4**). In the PAM-GELMA hydrogel, the Young's modulus was 446 ± 51.32 kPa, tensile strength of 44.7 ± 10 kPa, and elongation at break was $15.43 \pm 2.01\%$, representing brittle nature.^[67,68] As the P123 was blended in the PAM-GELMA hydrogel, Young's modulus gradually decreased while the tensile strength and elongation increased, which can be attributed to increased flexibility. The results are consistent with Loh et al.^[69]

Under the application of tensile strain, the covalently crosslinked PAM-GELMA hydrogel's network is broken, resulting in permanent deformation. However, in DN hydrogel, the P123 offers a primary network that partially unzips under tensile strain, thus keeping the PAM-GELMA networks intact.^[70] Therefore, as the concentration of P123 increased, the mechanical properties of the PAM-GELMA hydrogel were enhanced. However, at 10 w/v% P123 concentration, the elongation was reduced due to a high P123 concentration, resulting in the anisometric micellar formation, producing a large micellar core that may be responsible for this behavior.^[49] The DN3 hydrogels exhibit the highest elongation of $149.45 \pm 10.56\%$ compared to other DN hydrogels (DN1, DN2, DN4); therefore, DN3 hydrogel was fur-

ther utilized for making nanocomposite hydrogel by incorporating ACP_CIT.

A further effect of ACP_CIT was analyzed on the mechanical properties of DN3 hydrogel by varying the concentration of ACP_CIT. As observed in **Figure 4B**, at low ACP_CIT (0.75 w/v%) concentration, the elongation of DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogel was enhanced to $181.7 \pm 0.07\%$, while the tensile strength (63.6 ± 10 kPa) and Young's modulus (60 ± 17.32 kPa) were reduced compared to pristine DN3 hydrogels.

Reducing Young's modulus and increasing elongation indicates that the DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels were more flexible than DN3 hydrogels.^[71] Further increasing concentration of ACP_CIT (1.5 w/v% and 3 w/v%) negatively affects Young's modulus, tensile strength, and elongation. The results are consistent with previous studies in literature; Kouhestani et al. have observed a decrease in tensile strength and Young's modulus by increasing the concentration of graphene oxide (above 4 w/v%) in Pluronic F127.^[72] Similarly, Jalageri and Kumar have shown that increasing hydroxyapatite concentration (above 2 w/v%) decreases the mechanical properties of polyvinyl alcohol and polyvinyl pyrrolidone-based hydrogels.^[73] Increasing the nanomaterial concentration enhances the mechanical properties of the hydrogel at low nanoparticle concentration, after which the properties reach a plateau.^[74]

This phenomenon results from the interplay between the molecular weight of the polymer and the ACP_CIT nanoparticles. Under the deformation, the nanoparticles absorb the applied stress, delaying the crack propagation by numerous flexible polymeric chains.^[75] The concentration of 0.75 w/v% ACP_CIT provided the best stretchability results. However, 1.5 w/v% and 3 w/v% ACP_CIT concentrations may agglomerate or have formed non-crosslinked regions in the hydrogel.^[76] At higher concentrations, nanoparticles can agglomerate into clusters, forming an inhomogeneous distribution within the hydrogel hampering crosslinking between the polymer chains.^[77,78] Therefore, com-

Figure 4. Tensile stress-strain curve of the prepared hydrogel. (A) Analyzing the effect of P123 concentration on the elongation of the SN hydrogel. (B) Analyzing the effect of ACP_CIT concentration on the elongation of the DN3 hydrogel. (C and D) Young's modulus, (E and F) Tensile strength, and (G and H) Elongation at break (%) of SN, DN, and NCDN3 hydrogels.

promised mechanical properties may be observed in DN3-ACP1.5 and DN3-ACP3 hydrogels. This highlights that the desirable effect of ACP_CIT was reached at a lower concentration of 0.75 w/v%. Engler et al. revealed that the osteoid matrix surrounding the cultured cells has a Young's modulus of 20–60 kPa, which promotes osteogenic differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells.^[79] The developed DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels possess Young's modulus within the range of 20–50 kPa, which can potentially be explored in BTE applications.

3.4. Oscillatory Shear Tests

Analyzing the LVE region is the first step in analyzing the viscoelastic properties of the hydrogel, as it indicates the range in which further steps need to be performed without destroying the sample structure.^[80] The amplitude sweep of all the synthesized hydrogels is shown in Figure 5A–I. The storage modulus (G') represents the elastic behavior of the material, indicating its ability to store energy when subjected to deformation. The loss modulus (G'') measures the viscous behavior of the materials, indicating dissipated energy as heat under deformation. When $G' > G''$, the material exhibits gel-like behavior. On the contrary, the material possesses fluid-like behavior when $G' < G''$.^[54] All the

synthesized hydrogels possess $G' > G''$, showing gel-like behavior. After the LVE region, the breakdown of the structure starts with the formation of microcracks. However, the viscoelastic behavior of the structure was well preserved; therefore, structural breakdown is a slow process. The increasing strain increases the micro-crack propagation and reaches where $G' = G''$, known as the crossover point. The 3D network completely ruptures after the crossover point where the hydrogel exhibits ($G' < G''$) fluid-like behavior.^[81]

The crossover point of Pluronic P123 hydrogel was very high (at 171.1% strain), indicating its ability to withstand strain-induced irreversible deformation. However, in the case of PAM-GELMA hydrogel, the crossover point is shallow (at 2.40% strain), which can be attributed to its brittle nature.^[82] However, when the P123 is blended in the PAM-GELMA hydrogels, the crossover point was enhanced, resulting in the ability to withstand strain-induced irreversible deformation. In the case of nanocomposite hydrogels, adding 0.75 w/v% ACP_CIT (DN3-ACP0.75) shows enhancement in the crossover point (at 16.15% strain) when compared to pristine DN3 hydrogel (at 12.9% strain) resulting in enhanced ability to withstand strain-induced irreversible deformation. However, as the concentration of ACP_CIT increases to 1.5 and 3 w/v%, the crossover points decrease to 12% and 5.1% strain, respectively,

Figure 5. Amplitude sweep and crossover point of all the synthesized hydrogels.

obstructing the ability to withstand strain-induced irreversible deformation.

A frequency sweep analysis was performed to evaluate the viscoelastic properties of the prepared hydrogels, as shown in **Figure 6A-I**. In **Figure 6A**, the frequency sweep of 20% P123 shows $G'' < G'$ at initial frequencies corresponding to sol-like behavior; however, with an increase in frequency, the moduli sharply increase, and the crossover point is achieved, after which the G' dominates over G'' ascertaining gel-like behavior.^[54,83]

The G' and G'' of the hydrogels were analyzed against the frequency of 1 Hz shown in **Figure 7A**. The P123 possesses very low G' (1904 ± 50 Pa) and G'' (1112.3 ± 28.5 Pa) corresponding to the characteristic of weak and soft material. On the contrary, the PAM-GELMA hydrogel has high G' (10916.6 ± 625.3 Pa) and G'' (4058.6 ± 213.8 Pa), corresponding to the high strength and brittle nature. By increasing the P123 in PAM-GELMA hydrogel

the G' value was less affected compared to the G'' value. The reduction in G'' means less energy is dissipated during deformation, indicating that the hydrogel behaves more elastic and less viscous. Therefore, as the concentration of P123 increases, the difference between the G' and G'' values shows increasing elastic behavior.^[84]

This phenomenon was observed until the P123 concentration of 7.5 w/v% in PAM-GELMA hydrogel (DN3) where the modulus was G' of 9799 ± 956.24 Pa and G'' of 663.5 ± 151.4 Pa. However, further increasing the P123 concentration to 10 w/v% in PAM-GELMA hydrogel (DN4), the decrease in the G' (7923.33 ± 691.12 Pa) and increase in G'' (700.6 ± 164.3 Pa) was observed, which can be obstructing the elastic behavior of the hydrogel. In DN4 hydrogel, the initial solution of P123 was 20 w/v%, which was diluted to a 1:1 ratio with PAM-GELMA solution in DN4 hydrogel. At 20 w/v% P123 concentration, the anisometric micelles

Figure 6. Frequency sweep of the synthesized hydrogels.

are formed due to more significant aggregation, resulting in a large micellar core.^[85] This large micellar size may be responsible for reducing the storage and loss modulus.^[86]

In the case of nanocomposite hydrogels at lower concentration of ACP_CIT (0.75 w/v%) in DN3 hydrogels (DN3-ACP0.75), reveals the G' of 9141 ± 2545 Pa and G'' of 341.3 ± 134.8 Pa. The incorporation of ACP_CIT (0.75 w/v%) decreases G' and G'' values, however the reduction in the G' was marginal while G'' values drastically decreased which may be responsible for enhancing elastic property. However, as the concentration of ACP_CIT (1.5 w/v%) increased in DN3 hydrogels (DN3-ACP1.5) drastically increased values of G' (17766.6 ± 2689.4 Pa) and G'' of (1034.9 ± 290.2 Pa) imparting rigidity to the hydrogel. A further increase in ACP_CIT concentration (3 w/v%) in DN3 hydrogels (DN3-ACP3) shows extreme enhancement on G' (22523.3 ± 6950 Pa) and G'' of (1422.6 ± 47.6 Pa), which may be responsible for compromising the mechanical properties.^[87,88]

The $\tan \delta$ analysis of all the synthesized hydrogels is shown in Figure 7C. $\tan \delta$ is the ratio of G'' to G' of viscoelastic material often used to analyze the damping properties of the material. It quantifies the ratio of energy dissipated as heat. In viscoelastic material, a higher $\tan \delta$ value (close to 1) indicates a higher proportion of energies dissipated as heat relative to the energy stored elastically. On the other hand, a lower $\tan \delta$ value indicates that more energy is elastically stored compared to dissipated energy.^[80]

The $\tan \delta$ of PAM-GELMA hydrogel was 0.37 ± 0.03 when analyzed at a frequency of 1 Hz, shown in Figure 7D. Increasing P123 concentration in PAM-GELMA hydrogels shows $\tan \delta$ of 0.28 ± 0.13 (DN1), 0.16 ± 0.01 (DN2), 0.067 ± 0.01 (DN3) and 0.09 ± 0.02 (DN4) respectively. This analysis observed that $\tan \delta$ values decreased till hydrogel DN3, where the P123 concentration was 7.5 w/v% in PAM-GELMA (DN3), which can be attributed to increased flexibility.^[89] However, when the P123 concentration

Figure 7. Analyzing storage (G') loss modulus (G'') at the frequency of 1 Hz (A). Evaluation of the $\tan \delta$ at 1 Hz (B). $\tan \delta$ analyzed all synthesized hydrogels at varying frequencies (C) and complex viscosity (D).

was increased to 10 w/v% in PAM-GELMA (DN4), the $\tan \delta$ value increased, thus hindering the damping properties and reducing flexibility.

In the nanocomposite hydrogels, the $\tan \delta$ values were 0.036 ± 0.05 (DN3-ACP0.75), 0.057 ± 0.008 (DN3-ACP1.5) and 0.067 ± 0.02 (DN3-ACP3). The $\tan \delta$ value of DN3-ACP0.75 was the lowest, which can be attributed to the higher elasticity. Increasing the concentration of ACP_CIT in DN3 hydrogels to 1.5 w/v% (DN3-ACP1.5) and 3 w/v% (DN3-ACP3) increases the $\tan \delta$ value, which can be attributed to the reduction in the damping properties. With the increase in the ACP_CIT concentration, the $\tan \delta$ value starts to increase, which can alter the crosslinking density and polymer chain mobility within the hydrogel, thus affecting the hydrogel's overall mechanical properties.

The complex viscosity of all the synthesized hydrogel decreased with an increase in frequency, demonstrating shear thinning behavior. Variations in the complex viscosities were observed with different concentrations of P123 and ACP_CIT in PAM-GELMA hydrogel.^[90] As shown in Figure 7D, an increase in P123 concentration in PAM-GELMA hydrogel led to a notable reduction in complex viscosity. Similarly, the addition of different ACP_CIT concentrations affected the complex viscosity of the DN3 hydrogels. The highest ACP_CIT concentration (DN3-ACP3) exhibited higher complex viscosity, followed by DN3-ACP1.5 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels.

The results from tensile strength analysis is consistent with the oscillatory shear tests, confirming that blending of P123 enhances the elasticity and mechanical properties of PAM-GELMA hydrogels. However, the performance of

P123 was concentration-dependent. In addition, the performance of ACP_CIT was also concentration-dependent. At deficient concentrations of ACP_CIT, enhancement in elasticity was observed. However, increasing the concentration decreased elasticity, possibly due to agglomeration or steric hindrance.^[91–93] The DN3 and its nanocomposite DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogel possesses osteoid matrix-like mechanical properties. Therefore, further analysis was performed on these two hydrogels.

3.5. Creep Recovery and Stress Relaxation Analysis

Creep and recovery behavior helps reflect the interaction of polymeric chains of the viscoelastic material, which helps to understand and analyze the deformation mechanism of the hydrogels. Therefore, the creep recovery analysis was performed to evaluate the interaction change among the polymer chain of the one DN3 and nanocomposite DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels, as shown in Figure 8A. The incorporation of ACP_CIT in DN3 hydrogel (DN3-ACP0.75) shows a positive effect on decreasing creep strain. The stress relaxation curves are presented in Figure 8B. The DN3 and nanocomposite DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels show rapid stress relaxations. However, the presence of ACP_CIT slowed the stress relaxation of DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels.^[94,95] Previous studies have shown hydrogel's stress relaxation dependency on water uptake capacity. Faster stress relaxation was observed, increasing water content, possibly due to synergy of factors such as 1) migration of more water, 2) softer polymer network enhancing matrix flow, and lesser stiffness.^[96]

Figure 8. Analyzing creep-recovery (A), stress relaxation (B), water uptake capacity (C), and photographs of dried and swelled DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels (D and E).

3.6. Water Uptake Capacity

The water uptake capacity of DN3 hydrogels and its composite DN3-ACP0.75 is presented in Figure 8C. Both the DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels grow double in size after swelling, as observed in Figure 8D,E. The incorporation of ACP_CIT in the DN3 hydrogel reduces the swelling ratio, which is consistent with existing literature.^[97] Compared to DN3 hydrogel, the lower water uptake capacity of DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogel may be attributed to the slower stress relaxation.

3.7. Thermoresponsive Behavior

The thermoresponsive hydrogel possesses two different types of crosslinks. One of the crosslinks is composed of a covalent net-

work, which is essential to maintaining the structural integrity of the hydrogel. On the other hand, the second crosslink is composed of a physical reversible network responsible for fixing the temporary shape. In this investigation, PAM-GELMA forms the covalently crosslinked network.^[98] The thermosensitive P123 forms reverse physical crosslinking when exposed to high temperature (70 °C), triggering the temporary shape formation when exposed to (4 °C), thus providing shape memory and recovery properties as shown in Figure 9. The DN3 hydrogels and its composite DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels were immersed in Milli-Q water for 24 h, then placed in 70 °C Milli-Q water for 2 min, allowing shape transformation. The transformed shape was immersed in 70 °C Milli-Q water for 2 min, allowing transformed shape fixation (temporary shape). For shape recovery, the temporary hydrogel was again immersed in 70 °C Milli-Q (Movie provided in

Figure 9. Temperature-induced shape memory behavior of DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels.

Figure 10. Fluorescent microscopy of rhodamine-phalloidin (red) and DAPI (blue) staining of MC3T3-E1 cells embedded in DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels.

Supporting Information). Herein, we could control and repeat shape memory and recovery for at least five cycles.

3.8. In Vitro Analysis

Rhodamine phalloidin and DAPI staining were performed to analyze the cytoskeleton (red) and the nucleus (blue) of MC3T3-E1 cells, as shown in **Figure 10**. Epifluorescent microscopy was performed on days 1, 3, and 7 to investigate the cytocompatibility of the hydrogel. The cell attachment on the hydrogel was observed on day 1. On day 3, the cells spread well and were distributed on both hydrogels. On day 7 the hydrogel was densely populated with cells, confirming the cytocompatibility of developed DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels.

4. Conclusion

A new thermoresponsive double-network (DN) nanocomposite hydrogel was synthesized using primary (Pluronic P123), secondary (PAM-GELMA) networks, and ACP_CIT. Initially, P123 was blended in PAM-GELMA hydrogel in different concentrations, and its effect on tensile strength and viscoelastic properties was analyzed. It was observed that the increasing concentration of P123 (7.5 w/v%) in PAM-GELMA hydrogel enhanced the mechanical properties. However, a higher concentration of P123 (10 w/v%) compromised the mechanical properties of PAM-GELMA hydrogel. Similarly, the concentration-dependent trend was observed while developing nanocomposite hydrogels where a low concentration of 0.75% ACP (DN3-ACP0.75) enhanced mechanical properties beyond which the mechanical properties were negatively affected. This study has shown that PAM-GELMA hydrogel's mechanical properties strongly depend on the Pluronic P123 concentration and ACP_CIT. Therefore, the mechanical properties can be tuned per the desired applications by tuning the Pluronic P123 and ACP_CIT concentration. The thermoresponsive behavior of the DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 allows shape

alteration, which can be further used in developing complex architecture. The DN3 and DN3-ACP0.75 hydrogels are suitable for cell encapsulation, as evident by *in vitro* studies, thereby highlighting their potential use in tissue engineering applications requiring enhanced mechanical and biological performance.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

A.I.: conceptualization, literature review, methodology, investigation, data curation, writing-original draft preparation. K.R.: writing-review and editing. A.R. B.: supervision, writing-review, resources, and editing. J.L.: supervision, writing-review, resources, and editing. All authors provided critical feedback and helped to shape the research, analysis, and manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

amorphous calcium phosphate citrate, double network hydrogels, gelatin methacrylate, macromolecular materials, nanocomposite, Pluronic P123, polyacrylamide, shape memory hydrogel

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